

3D Partitioning in SPECSEM3D Internal Mesher

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Abstract

The SPECSEM3D package simulates seismic wave propagation using a parallel implementation of a variation of the Galerkin procedure called Spectral Element Method (SEM). The advantage of this method is that it produces a diagonal mass matrix which allows for quick explicit solving of the seismic wave equations. The drawback is that using an explicit method the solver is not stable unless the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition for convergence holds, imposing a certain inequality relation between the time step and spatial size of the spectral elements. The internal mesher provided with the package uses a partitioning approach that directly links the number of parallel solver tasks with the spatial size of the elements. For any given mesh, increasing the number of parallel processes leads to decreasing the element size, and via the CFL condition to decreasing the time step. This directly compromises the scalability of the solver by requiring more time steps for the same amount of work with no gain in performance. The goal of this project is to improve the scalability of the package by reconsidering the partitioning approach of the internal mesher. We analyze the existing approach and propose a new one, based on using the SCOTCH partitioning library, already integrated in the workflow for solving the problem on *externally* generated mesh. Our results indicate that the modified partitioning scheme leads to substantial performance benefits for regional modeling with the internal mesher in petascale environments. We validate the results by running the examples included in the package and observe that the solver produces identical synthetic seismograms when run with meshes generated by the original and modified internal mesher.

1. Introduction

The SPECSEM3D package [1] simulates forward and adjoint seismic wave propagation at local or regional scale on arbitrary unstructured hexahedral meshes. It uses the Spectral Element Method (SEM), a high-order finite element method introduced in [2], which is being actively researched, extended and applied in the geological context by Komatitsch, Tromp, Chaljub, Vilotte, Chen, Savage and others [3], [4], [5], [6]. The simulations can account for effects due to lateral variations of compressional and shear wave speed, acoustic and elastic material properties and density and allows the incorporation of 3D crustal, topography and bathymetry models. Full 21-parameter anisotropy [7] and lateral variations in attenuation [8] are also supported. The package won the Gordon Bell award for best performance at the SuperComputing 2003 conference in Phoenix, Arizona (USA) [9]. It was a finalist again in 2008 for a run at 0.16 petaflops (sustained) on 149,784 processors of the ‘Jaguar’ Cray XT5 system at Oak Ridge National Laboratories (USA) [10]. It also won the BULL Joseph Fourier supercomputing award in 2010.

As of version 2.0, meshing can be accomplished by using an external mesher like CUBIT, GiD, Gmsh, or by using the package’s own internal layer cake mesher. While the external mesher approach allows the researcher to specify the mesh exactly as he/she wants it, it requires specific knowledge of the mesher UI, writing automation scripts, e.g. in Python language and possibly other non-geophysical skills. It might prove too difficult for many geophysicists to manipulate the meshing software and its use would involve additional learning curve and/or implied cost (CUBIT and GiD are commercial software packages). On the other hand, the internal mesher provides an abstraction that is much closer to the geophysicist’s notions – it works with 2D maps of the interfaces between layers, 3D lateral variation numeric models, definition of the material properties in different layers, etc. All

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required input for the internal mesher is supplied in easily generated text files, which are supposedly readily available to the researcher via other means. Thus, the internal mesher is still a very attractive choice for pure geophysicists.

There is also a difference between external and internal meshing in the partitioning approach used for parallel task assignment. The workflow for dealing with external meshes includes a step that partitions the mesh into arbitrary desired number of chunks; the chunks are then processed by the solver in parallel by a corresponding number of processes. This partitioning is performed by the SCOTCH library [11] throughout the whole 3D domain of the mesh. The internal mesher employs a different hand-crafted technique – it partitions its mesh into “slices” – entire columns of spectral elements that span from the bottom to the top of the mesh. A processor is then given an entire column or slice, resulting in 2D-based pencil-like partitioning.

The 2D partitioning used in the internal mesher leads to poor solver scaling for regional models on large petascale machines. This is due to the fact that the solver uses an explicit Newmark- β time-marching scheme, which is a subject to the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) convergence condition: in order for the calculation to be stable, the time step should be smaller than the time it takes the seismic wave to travel across the spectral element. For any given mesh, increasing the number of processors reduces the spatial dimensions of the slices’ surfaces, and doing so beyond certain threshold requires reduction of the time step in order for the CFL condition to hold. Reduced time step means more steps are needed to cover the time span of the problem, and this undermines the increased performance introduced by the additional processors. This is not much of a problem for whole-earth simulations (as is the case in the aforementioned competitions, e.g. in [10]), where the spectral elements are rather large, but is problematic for meshes for regional simulations that span several hundred kilometers, where the stability threshold can be easily reached when using thousands of processors.

The above discussion outlines the goal of this project: **to improve the scalability of the package on petascale machines for internally generated meshes of regional models.**

2. Problem Analysis

The internal mesher is parameterized via a text file which includes several directives that relate to our discussion. These are:

- The region covered by the mesh, given in min/max Latitude/Longitude coordinates on Earth’s surface. The East-West axis is denoted as ζ and the North-South axis is denoted as η :
 - LONGITUDE_MIN (ζ_0);
 - LONGITUDE_MAX (ζ_1);
 - LATITUDE_MIN (η_0);
 - LATITUDE_MAX (η_1);
- The depth of the mesh in km below surface DEPTH_BLOCK_KM (ζ);
- The number of spectral elements along edges of the mesh at the surface: NEX_XI (N_ξ) and NEX_ETA (N_η);
- The number of MPI processors along ξ and η directions: NPROC_XI (P_ξ) and NPROC_ETA (P_η). The number of elements along each edge must be a multiple of the number of MPI processors along the same edge:

$$N_\xi = nP_\xi \quad N_\eta = mP_\eta, \quad (1)$$

where n and m are positive integers. The interpretation of these numbers is that each MPI task will have to process nm spectral elements at the surface of the mesh.

- A flag that indicates whether the mesher should produce regular or irregular mesh. The regular mesh contains exactly the same number of elements in each vertical layer: $N_\xi N_\eta$. This has the drawback that the accuracy is not the same in all elements, since wave speeds are different at the different layers, and in order to cope with this the number of elements near the surface must be larger than the number of elements deeper in the block. An irregular mesh contains one or two doubling layers at which the number of spectral elements above the layer is 4 times as much as the number of elements below it. For irregular mesh, in addition to (1) above, the following stricter relation must be observed:

$$n = 8k \quad m = 8p, \quad (2)$$

where k and p are positive integers. In this case, an MPI task processes $4kp$ elements at the bottom layers of the mesh, $16kp$ elements at the layers above the first doubling region, and $64kp = nm$ elements above the second doubling region and at the surface.

- The number of layers in vertical direction (N_ζ) is given by a more elaborate setup involving the definitions of different regions in the mesh and the number of layers in each region.

The solver parameter Δt (Δt) denotes the time step length in seconds. Since the solver uses the explicit Newmark- β method, the time step is subject to the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) stability condition [12]:

$$\Delta t < C \min_{\Omega}(h/v), \quad (3)$$

where C is an empirically chosen Courant number, which in our case is ~ 0.3 , Ω is the model volume, h is the distance between neighboring mesh points and v is the wave speed according to the model parameters. h depends on the spatial size of the corresponding spectral elements and the number of Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre mesh points along the edge of the element, which is defined as a constant in the source files (NGLL = 5). Empirical studies and examples in [12] suggest a spatial extent of about 1.88 km corresponds to a time step of about 11 ms.

Given (1) and (2) above, it is evident that increasing the number of processors will lead to either increase in the number of spectral elements or decrease of n , correspondingly m . In the case of $n=m=1$, the only option is to increase the number of spectral elements. Since the spatial extent of the surface of the mesh remains the same, this leads to smaller h and via (3) to smaller Δt .

A typical case is the Southern California model (socal1D) given in SPECSEM3D's distribution examples. For this model we have the following parameters:

- The mesh extends in E-W direction from -121.6° to -114.7° longitude for an average of 631.65 km;
- The mesh extends in N-S direction from 32.2° to 36.8° latitude for an average of 515.5 km;
- Depth of the block is 60 km;
- Number of spectral elements along the edges on the surface is $N_{\xi}=336$, $N_{\eta}=288$. Given the extent of the mesh, the average face of a spectral element on the surface is 1.88 km \times 1.79 km
- Number of MPI processors along the edges on the surface is $P_{\xi}=14$, $P_{\eta}=12$ for a total of 168 MPI tasks. By equation (2) this gives $n = m = 24$ and $k = p = 3$. Each MPI task processes 576 spectral elements at the surface and 9 at the bottom of the mesh.
- In vertical direction the mesh is divided into 12 layers without counting the layers introduced by the doubling of the mesh. This gives an average height of a spectral element to about 5 km. However, this is irrelevant, since each MPI task is processing all the layers of spectral elements that fall into its slice anyway;
- The time step Δt is set to 12 ms
- On the IBM Blue Gene/P machine at NCSA, Sofia, using 42 compute nodes in Virtual Node mode (= 168 virtual nodes), the solver simulates 10 seconds (840 time steps) of event time in about 410 seconds;

In the above example, without changing the spatial size and the time step, we can set k and p to their minimum value of 1, which leads to $m = n = 8$ and $P_{\xi}=52$, $P_{\eta}=36$ for a total of 1512 CPUs. Thus, we can introduce 9 times more CPUs without changing the spatial size of the elements and consequently the time step. If we try to increase the CPUs from here on, we will have to reduce the spatial dimensions in one of the directions, which by (3) will lead to reduction of the time step and consequently to increasing of the number of time steps. The solver cannot scale beyond 1512 CPUs for the given model surface area. On the other hand, hypothetically, if we could perform 3D partitioning of the mesh and divide also the 60 km of block depth into let's say 32 elements, each of them ~ 1.875 km high, we would potentially be able to utilize $1512 \times 32 = 48,384$ CPUs.

3. Method

The schematic workflow for a SPECSEM3D simulation is shown of Fig. 1. As seen on the figure, the workflow is different for external and internal meshes. External meshes are processed by `xdecompose_mesh_SCOTCH` tool, which uses the SCOTCH library to perform full 3D mesh partitioning, while the internal mesher includes the ad-hoc slicing described above that results in 2D pencil-like partitioning. The obvious solution is presented on Fig. 2, and that is to unify the workflows for internal and external meshers and modify the internal mesher so that it produces output used by the `xdecompose_mesh_SCOTCH` in order to perform partitioning.

The methodology adopted for petascaling the application is to analyze the internal mesher's slicing algorithm, understand its inputs and outputs, and then add output routines that can produce input for `xdecompose_mesh_SCOTCH`. While doing so, we also keep the original output routines and introduce a new command-line argument, which instructs it to work in the new mode. The internal mesher can thus work in two modes – when invoked without any command-line arguments the mesher works in the original mode as pictured on Fig. 1 (a). When invoked with the `--with-scotch` command-line argument, the mesher works in the modified mode as pictured on Fig. 1 (b).

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic workflow for a SPECSEM3D simulation in the original package; (b) Modified workflow with SCOTCH partitioning integrated in the internal mesher workflow (Source: (a) SPECSEM3D User Manual; (b) own work based on (a))

Another approach would be to incorporate the workings of `xdecompose_mesh_SCOTCH` into the mesher, thus skipping an extra processing step. The first approach however allows for quicker re-partitioning of the same mesh, without having to re-create the mesh regions again. Such a situation is applicable for stable models; for models still being actively researched the extra step should not be a big problem – after all it appears in the external mesher workflow anyway.

For the sake of simplicity and faster proof-of-concept we chose to implement the new mode of the mesher as a serial program. There are no reasons why it cannot be re-worked as a parallel program if such needs arise. However, our tests show that for a typical regional mesh ($\sim 350,000 \text{ km}^2$) the serial version is quite fast and finishes for a couple of minutes.

Apart from propagating the new mode to the various subroutines and handling the parallel vs. serial case for the two modes, the main changes to the internal mesher are in the `create_regions_mesh` subroutine. At its end, in the modified mode, instead of calling `save_databases` (which produces output suitable for `generate_databases` program), it calls a new subroutine, `save_mesh_files_SCOTCH`, which saves the 10 files expected by `xdecompose_mesh_SCOTCH`. The internal structures that are used to encode the mesh in memory are transformed in suitable way as to produce the proper output files.

4. Results

The modified internal mesher is validated against the `socal1D` model provided with the SPECSEM3D package, whose parameters are given in Section 2 above. We can report that semantically the results are correct and the solver deterministically produces identical seismograms for identical simulations performed through the original and the modified mesher. Table 1 below shows a performance comparison between runs of the same model using the original and the modified mesher. The excellent scalability of solver is evident, both when using the original and the modified mesher. However, when using the original mesher, the solver cannot scale beyond 1512 CPUs without changing the time step and thus compromising the scalability. On the other hand, the modified mesher case scales well up to 8192 CPUs, the maximum on the machine used for the tests: a 2-rack IBM Blue Gene/P at NCSA, Sofia. Figure 2 provides a graphical overview of the results. It should be noted that the scaling coefficients given are relative to 42, which is the minimal processors configuration tested; for less processors the times become unreasonably large. Our calculations show that the maximum number of processors that can be utilized for this model using the modified mesher and without changing the time step is 48,384. This number is produced by multiplying the 1512 processor limit in the original 2D decomposition mode by 32 elements in vertical direction: 60 km depth divided by 32 gives element height of about 1.88 km, which satisfies the CFL condition for the 12 ms time step.

Table 1. Comparison between performance of the solver with identical models, using the original and the modified internal mesher.

# MPI tasks	Ideal Scaling	Solver with original mesher		Solver with modified mesher	
		Time, s	Scaling	Time, s	Scaling
42	1	1725.4774	1	1732.5719	1
84	2	864.0562	1.9969	867.0336	1.9982
126	3	574.4727	3.0035	578.4470	2.9952
168	4	435.8337	3.9590	438.2663	3.9532
252	6	292.1359	5.9064	292.7629	5.9180
378	9	208.7452	8.2659	199.7226	8.6748
504	12	154.5895	11.1616	147.5648	11.7410
756	18	105.1435	16.4106	98.5674	17.5775
1512	36	53.3412	32.3479	51.4737	33.6593
2048	48.7619	n/a	n/a	41.0891	42.1662
4096	97.5238	n/a	n/a	21.1432	81.9446
8192	195.0476	n/a	n/a	11.6493	148.7275

5. Conclusion

The achieved results are very much relevant to the stated goals of the project. We hope that the modified package will help the geophysical community to perform faster simulations of regional models and thus be able to further advance the field of study.

The improved scalability limit will make the internally meshed regional models suitable for large-scale runs on Tier 0 systems. In the light of increased petascale resource availability due to PRACE and related projects, this optimization will spare the geophysical community:

- the effort to deal with non-trivial mesh generators;
- the price of commercial mesh generators;
- the time they wait on realistic regional simulations when using suitably large petascale resource partitioning;

It is planned that the owners of the source code are to be contacted and the modified internal mesher presented to them for review and possibly inclusion in the software package distribution. The modified implementation is available from the author upon request and will also be placed in the centralized PRACE project repository.

Related white papers regarding SPECSEM3D in PRACE deliverables include [13].

Fig. 2. Graphical comparison between performance of the solver with identical models, using the original and the modified internal mesher.

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